

Preservation for Dataverse in Canada

Recommendations Report

June 2021

*By Corey Davis, Carrie Breton, Doug Brigham, Rebecca Dickson,
Evan Echols, Grant Hurley, Beth Knazook, Mireille Nappert, Lee
Wilson, Jess Whyte*

Prepared by the Portage Network Preservation Expert Group for the
New Digital Research Infrastructure Organization (NDRIO)

NDRIO
New Digital
Research Infrastructure
Organization

NOIRN
Nouvelle organisation
d'infrastructure de
recherche numérique

portage
SERVICES PARTAGÉS POUR LES DONNÉES DE RECHERCHE
SHARED STEWARDSHIP OF RESEARCH DATA

engagedri.ca

portagenetwork.ca

Table of Contents

- Introduction..... 2
- Preservation of Research Data..... 2
- Environmental Scan..... 3
- Recommendations 5
 - 1. Support Institutional Policy Development 5
 - 2. Ensure a Minimum Preservation Capability (Level 1 Preservation): Bit-level preservation of datasets..... 5
 - 3. Provide Access to Enhanced Preservation Services (Level 2 Preservation): Support the creation and storage of Archival Information Packages (AIPs)..... 6
 - 4. Provide Strategic Funding to Develop these Preservation Services through: 6

Introduction

This report articulates a preservation recommendation for [Scholars Portal Dataverse](#) that involves connecting institutional subscriber Dataverse repositories to robust and replicated long-term storage of datasets in the [Ontario Library Research Cloud](#) (OLRC), ensuring a minimum level of reliable repository storage underlying Dataverse to support “preservation in place” (here understood as bit-level preservation and reliable fixity checking), while also providing those repositories with the ability to select datasets and create their own [Archival Information Packages](#) (AIPs) via an [Archivematica](#) pipeline, which would support the more robust preservation activities required for the long-term maintenance of research data.

Preservation of Research Data

As described in the recent [NDRIO White Paper](#), authored jointly by the Portage Preservation Expert Group and the Canadian Association of Research Libraries (CARL) Digital Preservation Working Group, the goal of digital preservation is to sustain access to data for as long as necessary. The work of digital preservation involves actively monitoring, planning, administering, and managing data, as well as related systems and workflows, all of which ensure persistence over time.¹ Good digital preservation practices also ensure the authenticity and reliability of the resources preserved.

Digital preservation activities ensure access over time by addressing risks such as:²

- The hardware or software required to interpret and present data becomes obsolete
- Data from an experiment that cannot be repeated is inaccessible or lost
- Data is not preserved with sufficient context, identifiers, and/or documentation

As such, digital preservation encompasses a wide range of activities to mitigate against these risks, including:

- Planning and developing strategies, policies, and workflows
- Liaising with data creators, data users, policy makers, and many others
- Ensuring repositories, preservation processing systems, and distributed preservation storage networks work together

Digital preservation infrastructure is a critical component of research data management and DRI more broadly. The Dataverse instances deployed across Canadian research institutions represent a suite of repositories, processing services, and storage infrastructure for depositing and discovering research data, but access to the more robust infrastructure needed for preserving research data at the scale demanded by the current research enterprise is sorely needed.

¹ <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/dpeg-what-is-dp>

² <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/dpeg-home/dpeg-risks>

This recommendation presents a two-tier, modular solution to support independently managed preservation activities at participating institutional Dataverse repositories. It allows for the fact that not all research data may require preservation processing and long-term storage, but all active repository data should be able to be retained for any length of time necessary to fulfill policy and legal obligations, have the appropriate mechanisms in place to validate the authenticity and reliability of that research data, and ensure that appraisal decisions to designate datasets for long-term preservation can be made at any point in the life of the resource.

Environmental Scan

There are several Dataverse-specific examples of shared preservation storage networks already established that we can look to:

- [Harvard Dataverse](#) (HDV)
Harvard's Dataverse runs on Amazon Web Services, using [S3](#) storage with a primary and mirrored instance. The data and metadata from those get backed up each night to Glacier and to Harvard's [Faculty of Arts & Sciences \(FAS\) Research Computing](#) centre (data and metadata are pulled down to FAS at Harvard's data centre using a custom script). This is a file system/data back-up service rather than a preservation workflow. Harvard has implemented API endpoints that allow for fixity checks, but these are not being used right now.
- [Qualitative Data Repository](#) (QDR)
The QDR uses a local file system linked to the [Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System \(iRODS\)](#) (an open source data management software) to push dataset directories to cloud preservation storage. A near-future development goal is to push [BagIt](#) bags to the file system instead, via Dataverse, so iRODS could replicate the bags in a preservation environment.
- [DataverseNL](#)
DataverseNL has implemented the Dataverse [SWORD API](#) functionality between the repository and the Dutch [Data Archiving and Networked Services \(DANS\)](#) long-term preservation (LTP) archive, EASY. Currently, in order to archive the data, a local administrator has to push a button to send the dataset to an LTP archive when needed. However, this will change in the near future so that all the versions of the data selected for long-term preservation according to [DANS' deposit requirements](#) will be automatically archived in the LTP archive. In the current workflow, metadata and data are stored in three different geographic locations and checksums are made when the data is archived. Regular fixity checks on those checksums are performed to ensure bit-level preservation of the archive. Storing in multiple locations ensures that when checksums fail, data stored at the other locations is available to replace the corrupted data.
- [Texas Data Repository](#) (TDR)
The Texas Data Repository makes use of the Texas Digital Library's infrastructure to connect Dataverse to the [Chronopolis Digital Preservation Network](#) via a DuraCloud instance. This

network was developed jointly by the UC San Diego Library, UC Santa Barbara, Emory University, Northwestern University and DuraSpace, with funding provided by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, to address an identified gap between digital preservation platforms and digital libraries.³ The TDR has made a commitment to ingest new content twice per year and keep it in Chronopolis for as long as necessary, unless there is a formal request to remove it. All Dataverse content is preserved across Chronopolis' three nodes in accordance with the Dataverse procedures originally created using zipped BagIt bags ([outlined here under "BagIt Export"](#)) and in accordance with TDR's [digital preservation and selection/appraisal policy](#).

- A tool to support preservation processing functionality for Dataverse is also available. Between 2015 and 2018, Scholars Portal sponsored Artefactual Systems Inc. to develop the ability for the preservation processing tool Archivematica to receive packages from connected Dataverse instances so that users of both tools can more easily process and create independent, standards-compliant archival packages from datasets uploaded to Dataverse. The integration between Dataverse and Archivematica was released as part of Archivematica 1.8 in 2018. More about the integration is available in the paper "[Integrating Dataverse and Archivematica for research data preservation](#)," on the Scholars Portal Archivematica demonstration sandbox [wiki page](#), and in Archivematica's [documentation](#).

In addition to the work being done to connect these Dataverse repositories to reliable, distributed archival storage, there is a growing recognition in the preservation community of the need for more collaboration in the development of preservation policies and actions, particularly as a wide variety of file formats and software environments are being collected as research data. Memory institutions have had a means of viewing and utilizing established preservation action plans through tools such as Archivematica's [Format Policy Registry](#), but such a tool relies on an individual institution's expertise in order to deploy alternative policy decisions. The [Preservation Action Registries](#) (PAR) is being developed in response to this need, with the goal of providing a system of best practice checks in the processing of archival information packages. PAR emerged from the Jisc Research Data Shared Service initiative, now operating as the [Open Research Hub](#), and is a joint initiative between Artefactual, Arkivum, Preservica, Jisc and the Open Preservation Foundation. Ensuring that institutional Dataverse repositories have access to an Archivematica pipeline and appropriate storage infrastructure will not only support long-term preservation, it will also strengthen preservation policy decision-making.

A related set of challenges involve supporting decision-making around which datasets to preserve and how. Individual Dataverse member institutions will need support in the development of tools

³ "UC San Diego Library Receives Mellon Grant to Develop Approaches to Preserving Digital Repositories," UC San Diego News Center. February 5, 2019. <https://ucsdnews.ucsd.edu/pressrelease/uc-san-diego-library-receives-mellon-grant-to-develop-approaches-to-preserving-digital-repositories>

and frameworks for preservation decision-making that are outside of the scope of Scholars Portal's responsibility as technical host. Such resources could include data deposit and collections policies to identify the datasets best suited for long-term preservation, levels of curation activity including metadata and dataset quality standards as a precursor to preservation, and policies for format migration and data retention periods.

We see Scholars Portal Dataverse, the OLRC, Portage/NDRIO as important players in facilitating collaboration. Connecting a distributed network of Dataverse repositories through preservation storage provides an opportunity to help individual subscribers implement policies and processing plans that align with best practices being developed across the country. The following recommendations are made in support of that goal.

Recommendations

1. Support Institutional Policy Development

- a. Improve policy infrastructure for Scholars Portal Dataverse, and recommend best practices for activities such as selection and curation that are the responsibility of individual Dataverse member institutions. This would increase the likelihood of well-articulated preservation policies across the participating institutions.
- b. Encourage succession planning
 - Develop a succession plan in partnership with the [Federated Research Data Repository](#) (FRDR), University of Toronto, or other institution.
- c. Provide certification support
 - It is recommended that NDRIO, through Portage, provide the necessary support and resources at the community level for individual repositories to achieve some level of certification, which may include a guide to self-assessment, a system for peer review, or help in achieving a certification standard such as [CoreTrustSeal](#).
 - Pursue a CoreTrustSeal certification for technical infrastructure for SP Dataverse generally when and if this type of certification is made available by CoreTrustSeal. In the meantime, document Scholars Portal Dataverse's technical, administrative and policy infrastructure using the current certification CoreTrustSeal standard, possibly as part of the [CoreTrustSeal certification pilot](#) being developed through Portage.

2. Ensure a Minimum Preservation Capability (Level 1 Preservation): Bit-level preservation of datasets

Enhance Dataverse repository storage with preservation functionality by:

- Establishing the OLRC as the default storage service for Dataverse in Canada and expanding OLRC nodes outside of Ontario to ensure geographic distribution of storage centres.
- Developing a proposed minimum level of preservation-friendly metadata for inclusion based on the recommendations of the [Dataverse North Working Group Metadata Best Practices Guide \(2.0\)](#).
- Supporting quarterly fixity checking of the objects in OLRC storage locations.
- Providing error reporting and notifications to individual Dataverse owners.

3. Provide Access to Enhanced Preservation Services (Level 2 Preservation): Support the creation and storage of Archival Information Packages (AIPs)

Ensure the national availability of Archivematica pipelines, enabling institutions to appraise, select, create, and store AIPs for identified datasets and to manage their AIPs according to local policy and procedures. This support could be provided by the following options:

- Expanding [Permafrost](#) or [Archivematica-as-a-Service \(AaaS\)](#) to [Bureau de coopération interuniversitaire \(BCI\)](#) institutions to ensure the availability of a hosted Archivematica service across all Canadian provinces. This would include enhancing the accessibility of Permafrost and AaaS through the development of a bilingual interface and documentation, and establishing bilingual technical support services.
- Installing a centralized Archivematica preservation pipeline hosted by Scholars Portal.
- Connecting AIP storage with the existing FRDR Preservation Pipeline so that Dataverse AIPs can be stored at a FRDR Preservation Service Provider (PSP).

4. Provide Strategic Funding to Develop these Preservation Services through:

- a. An initial investment by NDRIO in sustainable storage
 - Building a collaborative network from the ground up requires, at a minimum, funds for the purchase of repository storage for the Level 1 & Level 2 Preservation options described above, including identification of storage needs and associated costs. Growth may be encouraged by fostering a consortia where institutions can share the costs of additional storage and maintenance going forward. This might be realized through the existing governance group that has formed to oversee Dataverse in Canada, or through an alternative network developed and supported by NDRIO and Portage. With time and

support, we see the service itself becoming a sustainable, member-funded enterprise.

- b. Funding for development work to improve the Dataverse-Archivematica integration, specifically the recommendations below:

- **Integrate dataset processing and reporting in Dataverse**

Currently, data curators must have direct access to both the Dataverse and Archivematica applications in order to select datasets for preservation processing. A push-to-preservation workflow in the Dataverse interface to automatically queue datasets for Archivematica processing would enable more seamless integration between the two applications. Similarly, information about whether a dataset has been processed successfully and stored for preservation is not currently available in the Dataverse application: a metadata field populated with this information would also make curation and preservation workflows smoother.

- **Scale dataset processing in Archivematica**

As with the FRDR-Archivematica integration, automated dataset processing will be critical to managing the growing volume of data being produced by Canadian researchers. At the moment, large datasets need to be broken up and managed manually to ensure they process successfully. Enabling an Archivematica administrator to cue up all datasets in a particular sub-Dataverse or folder at the institutional or collection level so that Archivematica can run through them automatically would reduce the burden on staff and improve processing times.

- **Fix open issues with Dataverse preservation metadata**

Several open issues ([1057](#), [1058](#)) affecting the representation of tabular data files in Archivematica-created METS/PREMIS files require resolution.

- **Facilitate a Globus integration with Archivematica's Storage Service**

A major barrier to the use of Archivematica in the ongoing management of large datasets is the lack of a [Globus](#) connector for the [Archivematica Storage Service](#). Globus is a file transfer mechanism by which very large datasets (up to and including petabytes of data) can be reliably and securely shared. Globus is the primary tool through which data is shared on FRDR, from depositors to end users, and this system is also used for moving AIPs between storage locations on the FRDR Preservation Pipeline. The Storage Service is a standalone web application that tracks files in various storage environments, used for managing the storage locations and packages for one or many Archivematica dashboards.

Since Globus cannot be integrated with the Archivemata Storage Service, AIPs cannot be easily searched and retrieved for re-processing, preventing the use of Archivemata's user-friendly features for re-ingest (which is critical to being able to support activities such as the versioning of datasets when requested by depositors), as well as easy mechanisms to manage AIP recovery processes and ongoing fixity checking.

A recent Scholars Portal development project, sponsored by CANARIE, provided a [proof-of-concept integration with Globus for Dataverse](#). A logical extension of this project would be to provide Globus support for the existing [Dataverse-Archivemata integration](#) to utilize Globus in the exchange of datasets between the repository and archival storage.

- c. Funding for Dataverse member staff training, on-boarding, and ongoing support
 - **Level 1 Funding:** Onboarding/training/support for Dataverse owners that explains minimum preservation metadata requirements, and outlines procedures for monitoring and addressing errors in fixity checking. This service is probably best carried out by Scholars Portal with the support of the Portage Network.
 - **Level 2 Funding:** Onboarding/training focused on implementation and use of the Archivemata-Dataverse integration, aimed at the users of Archivemata-as-a-Service, Permafrost, and locally-run Archivemata pipelines. Technical support could be facilitated by Scholars Portal and COPPUL, while the Portage Network could ensure access to bilingual services and documentation. This would need to include support for policy development at the institutional level for decisions outside of the scope of Scholars Portal's role as a technical host, such as curation workflows, selection for preservation, and retention periods.